

CAPTURING GUIDELINES FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY

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BACKGROUND

Digital cultural heritage refers to the use of digital technologies to preserve, document, and share the cultural heritage of society. It encompasses a wide range of activities, from digitizing historical documents and artifacts to creating virtual exhibitions and online educational resources. In today's fast-paced and constantly evolving digital world, the importance of digital cultural heritage cannot be overstated.

One of the main benefits of digital cultural heritage is that it makes cultural resources more accessible to a wider audience. Traditional methods of preserving and sharing cultural heritage, such as physical museums and archives, can be limited by factors such as location, cost, and opening hours. Digital technologies, on the other hand, allow cultural heritage to be accessed by anyone with an internet connection, regardless of where they are located. This democratization of access to cultural heritage is particularly important for marginalized communities who may have been historically excluded from participating in the preservation and sharing of their own cultural heritage.

Another important aspect of digital cultural heritage is its ability to preserve cultural heritage for future generations. Many physical artifacts and documents are at risk of deterioration, loss, or destruction due to factors such as natural disasters, human conflict, and neglect. Digitizing these resources ensures that they will be preserved in a format that can be easily replicated and stored for future generations to access and learn from.

Additionally, digital cultural heritage allows for new forms of engagement and interpretation of cultural heritage. Virtual and augmented reality technologies can be used to create immersive experiences of historical sites and artifacts, allowing visitors to gain a deeper understanding and appreciation of the cultural heritage in question. Similarly, digital tools such as crowdsourcing and citizen science can be used to engage the public in the process of documenting and preserving cultural heritage, creating a sense of ownership and stewardship among members of the community.

Digital cultural heritage is a vital tool in the preservation, documentation, and sharing of cultural heritage. It allows for a wider audience to access and engage with cultural heritage, ensures the preservation of cultural heritage for future generations, and enables new forms of interpretation and engagement. It is crucial that society continues to invest in and prioritize digital cultural heritage efforts.

DISCLAIMER

The following guidelines for the photography of cultural heritage objects describe the most important basics of digital photography in general and the specific techniques necessary to successfully process the image files in an "Image-Based Modeling" (IBM) software. Image-Based Modeling - more commonly referred to as "Photogrammetry" or "Structure from Motion Photogrammetry" (SfM) - uses highly efficient algorithms (e.g. SfM, multiview stereo, mesh-reconstruction, texture synthesis) to create a textured 3D model from imported image files (Tan 2020). In doing so, the software mainly relies on the pixel data of the imported source files. This means that the quality of the 2D photo images plays the most significant role in creating a high-quality 3D model in IBM software. The guidelines are restricted to the photographic recording of small to medium-sized objects using so-called "close-range photogrammetry". Because the workflow of processing image data to generate a 3D model is always object-specific, a uniform solution to work with IBM software can only be presented to some extent.

23/05/05 vc, virtual culture

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1. INTRODUCTION

Software

You need to install an "Image-Based Modeling" (IBM) software, for example Agisoft, Metashape, Reality Capture and Meshroom. Image-Based Modeling - more commonly referred to as "Photogrammetry" or "Structure from Motion Photogrammetry" (SfM) - uses highly efficient algorithms (e.g. SfM, Multiview stereo, mesh-reconstruction, texture synthesis) to create a textured 3D model from imported image files. In doing so, the software mainly relies on the pixel data of the imported source files. This means that the quality of the 2D photo images plays the most significant role in creating a high-quality 3D model in IBM software.

No matter what software you choose, the pictures you make decided on the quality of the final result you can hardly create a good model with bad photographs.

Computer

The computer for capturing must not be capable of processing the 3D results. Using a computer to remote control the camera in the capturing process is advantageous. Most camera manufacturers offer application for that purpose. For the pater processing, an independent and more powerful workstation with good specifications is used.

"The basic utensils are:

- CAMERA
- LENSES
- LIGHTS
- COLOUR CHECKER
- SCALE / TARGETS
- BACKGROUND
- COMPUTER
- TURNTABLE"

2. EQUIPMENT

2.1 CAMERA

2.2 LENSES

DSLR Cameras

For photogrammetry, a digital DSLR or mirrorless camera with average resolution and minimal distortion is recommended. The camera must offer manual controls. Some popular camera models for photogrammetry include the Canon EOS 6D, the Sony A7R III, and the Nikon D810.

Camera Stand or Tripod

It is also essential to have a consistent camera setup and stable platform for capturing images to ensure accurate results. It is recommended to use a solid camera stand or tripod. Ideally, the camera stand easily allows for adjusting the camera height.

Resolution

It is not necessary to have the highest resolution possible. Pixel count bigger than 50 MPixel results in a large file size. In combination with the number of images needed for photogrammetry, the total data volume can slow down processing without significantly improving the quality of the final 3D model and possibly even generating more noise in the point clouds.

Lenze Specifications

For photogrammetry, a standard or wide-angle lens is recommended. Such a lens allows you to capture a larger field of view, vital for capturing enough information to create accurate 3D models. Additionally, lenses with minimal distortion will help ensure the captured images are as precise as possible. Therefore, it is recommended to use fixed-focus macro lenses optimised for close-up photography. A conventional lens is optimised with the focal plane at infinity. Since in most cases the distance between the camera and the object is only a few meters, a lens for close distances is recommended.

Aperture

The aperture size in f-stops is convoluted with unsharpness resulting from diffraction caused by the size of the aperture. Diffraction occurs when light passes through a small aperture, causing the light rays to bend and spread out, which results in a decrease in image sharpness. As aperture size decreases diffraction increases, causing the sharpness to decrease. As a result, using a wider aperture helps to minimise diffraction and produce sharper images.

However, it's important to note that the aperture should be selected based on the desired depth of field and lighting conditions.

In photogrammetry, you have to balance the aperture size with the desire for a deeper depth of field and the need for a sharper image. In most cases, using the lowest f-stop possible is recommended while still achieving the desired depth of field. Therefore it is crucial to take many overlapping images in which only a local part of the artefact is shown.

Lens Calibration

Some Image-Based Modeling (IBM) solutions such as Metashape offer a simple automatic lens calibration, which is required for each camera lens pairing. Lens calibration is necessary to adjust the focus and alignment of a lens. To do this, a black-and-white pattern displayed on the screen must be photographed from various angles. By importing the photos into the software, distortions and focus inaccuracy can be automatically corrected to some extent.

2.3 COMPUTER

2.4 LIGHTS

2.5 TURNTABLE

2.6 BACKGROUND

2.7 COLOURCHECKER

2.8 SCALE / TARGETS

Remote Control

Using a computer to remote control the camera in the capturing process is advantageous. Most camera manufacturers offer an application for that purpose. Nikon, for example, offers the software Capture Pro. Also, photography software like Adobe Lightroom allows remote control of a camera.

The applications allow one to control the camera settings and check the preview image in a live view mode. The computer also helps store captured images for later processing. The computer for capturing must not be capable of processing the 3D results. An independent and more powerful workstation with good specifications is used for that purpose.

Light Specifications

Use powerful studio light equipment with a spectral power distribution of daylight, e.g. D55. LED light as well as Xenon flash is well suited for this application. Choosing LED or flash depends on the size of the object and the illumination power needed. For larger artefacts or capturing in situations with a high level of ambient light, it is recommended to use a flashlight because of the power available.

Lux

The flashlight does not harm the original because of the short illumination duration ($< 1/10'000$ s). This is important to mention because the measured value of light exposition is Lux. Lux is not taking into account the time of exposition and is therefore not recommended to be applied with a flashlight.

Recording small objects using a manual or an automatic remote-controlled turntable can be helpful to speed up the capturing process. The camera position (only changing in height and vertical angle) and background (see section h.) stay fixed while the object turns. Modern turntable systems like Syrp (Manfrotto), Foldio 360 (Orangemonkie) or Puluz 360 (Puluz) can remotely be controlled by mobile apps, the computer and DSLR cameras using Bluetooth or infrared communication.

Minimum PC specifications

Processor: Intel Core i7 or i9, Apple M1/M2, or equivalent AMD Ryzen CPU

RAM: 16 GB or more

Graphics card: Dedicated NVIDIA or AMD GPU with 4 GB or more VRAM

"Light is the most important matter of photography. Make sure to use high quality light sources."

A homogeneous background should be used for the shooting process, preferably a backdrop system that contrasts in colour with the object. If this is not possible, for example, if you do not use a turntable but move the camera around the object, you should make sure that nothing changes in the background, as this can affect the feature detection in the photo-alignment process of the IBM-software.

2.6 BACKGROUND

Realistic Colours

A neutral and true-to-life colour reproduction is essential for the reproduction of artworks. A colour checker allows you to calibrate the colours in your images to match the actual colours of the scene. It helps to ensure consistent colour between different shoots, cameras, and lighting conditions.

Colour Space

It is recommended to take one first image of the Colour-Checker for later calibration of the image data. The aim is to have a high-fidelity colour reproduction in the 3D space. The destination colour space is sRGB for all 3D workflows.

2.7 COLOURCHECKER

Scaling

The scaling of a 3D model is crucial in photogrammetry. Without an indication of size and proportions dimensions are intangible to the viewer, especially if the original is unknown. The creation of the 3D model in photogrammetry is not directly based on measurement data, e.g. in scanning technologies. Still, on pixel data, it's necessary to scale the model during processing in IBM software. Precautions must already be taken during the object acquisition process. For this, either calibrated scale bars can be placed within the scene, the distance between characteristic points on the original can be measured and later referenced, or the distance measurements between encoded targets can be used.

Targets

Coded targets are uniquely identified black and white patterns encoded in 12, 16 or 20 bits. They are automatically identified on the image files by the software and provide not only the ability to scale the object but also assist the software in estimating the camera location of the object's position.

2.8 SCALE / TARGETS

"Use a background with enough contrast, that separates the artifact well."

3. STAGE PREPARATION

3.1 ILLUMINATION

Photographic images for 3D modelling do not obey the exact requirements of conventional photos. In contrast to classical photography, photogrammetry imaging aims to create a homogeneous and neutral image of the original. The goal of illumination is to detect identical motif parts in all captured images. In addition, it is essential not to create too strong a shadow effect since these shadows would be part of the texture created later.

The right image shows too much shadow, whereas the left image is illuminated homogenous, without losing details of the structure of the surface (source: www.truvis.ch).

- Illuminate the original with standard light of Type D55, or D60
- Make sure that no ambient light interferes
- Use large softboxes or a white capturing cube to ensure homogeneous illumination of the artefact
- In the case of large indoor objects, it is possible to use, e.g. a white wall or ceiling as a giant reflector
- Make sure that shadows are limited

3.2 PERSPECTIVE

The perspective defines the camera's position relative to the scene/object. Make sure the camera is set so that it covers the whole or parts of the original. In the capturing process, the artefact usually will be rotated on the capturing stage, with the camera in a fixed position, if the object is light enough to use a turntable. The capturing then is repeated from other camera heights. For smaller objects three levels of height and about 30 positions on the rotating stage are ideal. It is said that an overlap of

approx. 60% of the images should be given. If an object has many detailed areas or areas that are difficult to access, it is advisable to take additional detailed images so that no missing parts appear in the calculated model geometry and texture. If the object is small, light and stable, it should be captured lying down or placed upside down to capture its base. The photos of the object's various sides can be combined in "IBM"-software to generate a complete 3D model.

4. CAPTURING

4.1 CAMERA SETTINGS

Exposure Mode

For reasons of exposure control and homogeneity, using the camera in Manual Mode (M) is essential. Only in Manual Mode the shutter speed and the aperture of the lens can be set in a controlled and fixed manner. In that way, it is possible to capture all images with the same exposure and the same depth of field.

Sync Time

When using the flashlight, setting the shutter speed to a minimal value is crucial. Make sure you set the camera's shutter speed to the minimal sync time (typically 1/250s for most SLR cameras). If you operate the camera by hand, ensure the exposure time is not changed to any shorter value by accident.

File Formats

For optimal adjustability in post-processing, store the images as RAW files with the maximum quantisation depth of the camera, e.g. 12 or 14 bits. Be aware that the RAW file format is not an archival master but only an intermediate file format for post-processing. If you want to store the captured files for any other application, choose TIFF or JPG2000 for sustainability.

ISO

A digital camera has a spectral sensitivity given by the sensor and the electronics. Adjusting the ISO settings only results in a gain applied to the signals. To get the best possible data, it is recommended to use the lowest standard setting for the ISO. Do not select lower settings than that to have some range for later adjustments of overexposure in the case of gloss.

AF

It is recommended to switch Auto Focus (AF) off, as complete control of the camera is wanted. Especially homogenous surfaces with little structure disturb a camera's auto-focus system. Because many images shall be captured in a short time, it is essential to eliminate sources of error, such as a plane of sharpness set wrong because of the AF system.

"It is critical to understand that the images captured do not need to fulfil the needs of the aesthetics of conventional photographic captures."

4.2 EXPOSURE SETTINGS

Histogram

To control exposure and avoid overexposure, the histogram is the best tool to be used. Ensure you do not exceed values of 255 on an 8-bit scale. If the scene's contrast is too big, use fill-light to reduce it. Fill light is best applied with large softboxes or indirect illumination, e.g. by using walls of the capturing room. Such ambient light is adjusted so that the scene contrast fits the camera's dynamic range ideally.

Shutter vs. Aperture

Sharp images are essential for photogrammetry. Sharpness is given by: The depth of field defined by the aperture and the overall sharpness given by the diffraction caused by the aperture. It is recommended to use the shortest possible shutter time that corresponds with the flashlight (sync-time). It also is recommended to work with the aperture closed. The f-stop value is defined by the pixel size of the camera used. A typical value of $f = 12 - 16$ is the limit that shall not exceed.

Sharpness

Sharpness is defined by the optical system and the subsequent software process of unsharp masking (or equivalent). It is essential to have optimal optical settings and only limited software sharpening; strong sharpening results in intense noise that reduces the usability of the images.

"The photographs are surface measurements; the only requirement is a maximum level of information of the original represented. Therefore it is generally essential to underexpose images slightly to make sure that also highly reflective parts are recorded with some structure. Overexposure must be avoided because overexposed areas do not have any content about the originals colour, shape or texture."

4.3 FOCUS/FOCUSTACKING

In most capturing situations, capturing the artefact in full sharpness is challenging. Especially objects with an expansion in z that is larger than the depth of field are problematic to capture in high quality.

There are two solutions:

1) Capture multiple images with different planes of focus and process them in a second step with a focus stacking software like TuFuse of ImageJ.

2) Use a tilt lens to adjust the plane of focus optimally.

4.4 COLOUR SETTINGS

To be compatible with any post-processing it is recommended to stay in sRGB space. Make sure the images are represented in sRGB (profile applied).

It is recommended to set the default colour rendering intent to "normal" "standard" or "neutral". This setting gives the best colour reproduction for most cameras out of the box. Use a colour target like the X-Rite colour checker only if you are thoroughly familiar with profiling a camera. Wrong input profiles lead to worse colour accuracy than most build-in profiles.

5. POST PROCESSING

5.1 RAW CONVERSION

The often memory-intensive RAW files (often DNG or NEF), if they are not already captured directly onto the computer, must be transferred from the camera to the computer, where they should be converted into lighter file formats such as TIFF or JPEG2000 using image processing software or image converters.

5.4 DATA TRANSFER

Store all files properly on at least two storage devices. Keep the RAW files until the entire processing is done and the result is visually convenient. Also, ensure that the adequately adjusted RAW files are converted to archival masters in TIFF or JPEG2000 if necessary.

5.2 NAMING

It is recommended to name the images sensibly systematically and to sort them into categorised folders already during the conversion, making them easier to find and classify, especially for others. There is no specific convention on how to name image files for further processing in image-based modelling software, but there are some recommendations which can be followed. The file name should contain the date and the name of the displayed object. The date should be formatted as "year, month and day" (YYYY.MM.DD). It is best to end the file name with the number of the respective image, depending on the number of image files, starting with 1, 01 or 001. If, for example, camera settings were altered to capture details or the object was turned to take images of the base of the thing, it is necessary to separate the images into multiple folders. If there are many sub-folders, they should be saved in a superordinate folder that includes at least the date and the object's name in its filename.

5.3 QUALITY CONTROL

Quality control of image quality can be done in most photogrammetry applications automatically. Make sure that exposure is correct and do a brief visual control of the images. Ensure proper naming and that all files belonging to a captured series are stored in a specific folder.

"After the capturing, some possibilities exist to optimise the image data for further processing. These are usually carried out within image processing software."

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<https://www.capturingreality.com/>
<https://alicevision.org/#meshroom>
<https://www.regard3d.org/>

Modeling, Texturing, Rendering

<https://www.blender.org/>
<https://www.autodesk.ch/de/products/3ds-max>
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